

BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES

GENERAL CHARACTERISTICS OF THE MYCOBIOTA OF VEGETABLES AND MELONS CULTIVATED IN THE SOUTHERN REGION OF AZERBAIJAN

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Abstract

The conducted studies revealed that some vegetables and melons used for food purposes in the southern region of Azerbaijan differ in the number and species composition of their mycobiota. During the analyzes, diseases caused by fungi in vegetables and melons were identified and the ways of their prevention were thoroughly studied, and the regularities of their growth, development, and spread were studied.

Keywords: vegetables and melons, pathogenic fungi, mycotoxins, phytosanitary condition, toxigens

Since the second half of the 20th century, humanity has begun to face manifestations such as a shortage of energy, nutrients, as well as raw materials for various production sectors. One of the main reasons for this is the constant increase in the world population and the fact that this process occurs within a fixed territory, as a result of which traditional food sources are no longer able to meet the growing demand day by day. Solving these issues, that is, eliminating the observed deficiencies, naturally specifies the tasks facing modern scientific fields, which currently cover two directions - the creation of new sources and increasing the efficiency of using existing sources. Against the background of the tasks set by research conducted in this direction, providing the world's population with agricultural products, primarily those obtained from vegetables and melons, is also in the spotlight. We know that plant products are an indispensable component of people's diet. Therefore, in the research conducted to provide the population with fresh vegetables and melons, high-yielding plant varieties have been created, and currently obtaining targeted products from them is considered one of the main ways out of food shortages. However, a certain portion of the products produced each year is lost for various reasons, among which diseases caused by various living things occupy a significant place, and it is no coincidence that extensive research is being conducted around the world today to prevent this.

Among these types of diseases, those caused by fungi are of particular importance, at least because during the outbreak of a disease caused by this or that fungus, the yield loss can reach 50%, and the annual yield loss caused by fungal diseases is measured in millions of tons. Naturally, in order to prevent diseases caused by fungi, their comprehensive study, the regularities of their growth, development, and spread should be comprehensively studied. At the same time, it is also very important to develop effective measures to combat them.

The important place occupied by the agricultural sector in the economy of the Republic of Azerbaijan, the widespread cultivation of vegetables and melons allow us to note that the above issues are also important

for our country. Thus, the richness of its nature, the diversity of natural climatic conditions have led to the spread of a number of disease-causing fungi in Azerbaijan, and a lot of research has been conducted on their study. Most of the research conducted mainly covered the study of pathogenic fungi that cause diseases in fruit plants and the main forest-forming tree species. Although research on the mycobiota of vegetable and melon plants has been conducted for a long time, the results of the research conducted so far do not allow us to generalize not only the mycobiota of vegetable and melon plants widely cultivated in Azerbaijan, but also of a specific variety.

If we add to what we have said that plant seeds also play a special role in the transmission of any disease caused by fungi, and this issue has generally been completely ignored in the studies conducted in Azerbaijan, then the necessity of conducting studies in this direction is beyond doubt.

In order to conduct the intended mycological studies, vegetables and melons such as cucumbers, eggplants, cabbage, potatoes, tomatoes, peppers, carrots, watermelons, melons, pumpkins, beans, peas, soybeans, etc. cultivated in the indicated areas of Azerbaijan were selected as the objects of study. For this purpose, samples were taken from the vegetative and generative organs of vegetables and melons cultivated in the indicated areas in the years of the study, which were likely to contain fungi. In taking samples, the methods of selecting permanent areas for planned routes and stationary observations, which are widely used in the course of mycological studies, were also used. Sampling was also carried out by season. In total, about 2,200 samples were taken during the research and, in accordance with the purpose of the study, were analyzed using mycological methods currently widely used in this type of work.

As a result of the analysis of samples taken from vegetable and melon plants cultivated in various zones of Azerbaijan, it was determined that the number of fungi distributed in the studied plants is 174 (more precisely, 173 species and 1 form), and their taxonomic structure is given in table.

Taxonomic structure of fungi isolated during the research

Class	Order	Division	Genus	Species
Oomycota	1	2	3	9
Zygomycota	1	1	2	7
Ascomycota	2	2	3	5
Bazidiomycota	2	2	4	8
Deyteromycota	3	6	27	145
Total	9	13	39	174

As can be seen, representatives of indeterminate fungi (Deuteromycota) predominate among those recorded. Thus, 80.3% of the fungi recorded during the research belong to this group. Representatives of the Oomycota department are in second place - 5.2%. The share of the Basidiomycota, zygomycota and ascomycota departments is 3.6%, 4.1% and 2.7%, respectively.

Among the recorded fungi, the largest number of species is represented by representatives of the Colletotrichum genus. Thus, as a result of research, 17 species of this genus (9.8% of the total species) are widespread in garden and melon plants cultivated in Azerbaijan. The genera Ascochyta, Phoma, Fusarium, Septoria and Penicillium can also be considered numerous, the number of which also varies between 11-14 species

When fungi common in vegetable and melon crops cultivated in different regions of Azerbaijan are grouped according to the mentioned system, it becomes clear that the numerical superiority is inherent in representatives belonging to the boreal type. Thus, 56.0% of the 168 species whose range has been determined belong to this type. The predominance of boreal elements among fungi recorded in vegetable and melon crops is a fact that has been confirmed in other studies conducted so far, that is, the leading role of the influence of the northern regions in the formation of the mycobiota determined for Azerbaijan is clearly felt. As a result of the conducted studies, the phytosanitary condition of the cultivated agrocenoses of vegetable and melon crops in Azerbaijan was assessed from a mycological point of view. It should be noted that there is no universal, that is, unambiguously accepted approach to the assessment of agrocenoses today, therefore, it was considered appropriate to use different approaches when assessing the phytosanitary condition of different cenoses.

References

1. Asan, A. (2011). Checklist of Fusarium species reported from Turkey. *Mycotaxon*, 116(1), 479.
2. Неверова О.А., Гореликова Г.А., Позняковский В.М. Пищевая биотехнология продуктов из сырья растительного происхождения. Новосибирск: Изд-во Сиб. ун-ва, 2007, 415 с.
3. Сартакова О.Ю. Промышленная микробиология. Барнаул: Из-во АлтГТУ, 2009, 173с.
4. Саттон Д., Фотергилл А., Риналди М. Определитель патогенных и условно патогенных грибов. М.: Мир, 2001, 486с.
5. Свириденко Г.М. Обеспечение безопасности и качества продуктов. // Сыроделие и маслоделие, 2004, № 1, с. 5–8.
6. Yusifova, A., Asadova, B., & Aslanova, S. (2024). Plants, Human Health And Civilization. *Norwegian Journal of Development of the International Science*, 136.
7. Aslanova, S. (2019). Flora and vegetation of the mountainous part of Lankaran. Printing house ADMIU.
8. Yusifova, A., Asadova, B., & Aslanova, S. (2024). SPECIES COMPOSITION AND RESOURCES OF CULTIVATED AND WILD FORAGE PLANTS IN AZERBAIJAN. *German International Journal of Modern Science/Deutsche Internationale Zeitschrift für Zeitgenössische Wissenschaft*, (84).
9. Jabraylzadeh, S., Aslanova, S., & Ismayilova, G. (2024). GENERAL CHARACTERISTICS OF PHYTOPATHOGENIC SPECIES OF FUNGAL BIOTA OF SOME MEDICINAL PLANTS FOUND IN THE FLORA OF TALYSH (AZERBAIJAN). *German International Journal of Modern Science/Deutsche Internationale Zeitschrift für Zeitgenössische Wissenschaft*, (84).
10. Gurbanov, E., & Aslanova, S. (2024). Average annual productivity of the Thymuseta-vicaetum-festucosum formation, distributed in summer pasture field No. 8" Turkesoba"(AZERBAIJAN). *Norwegian Journal of Development of the International Science*, 126.
11. Yusifova, A., Aslanova, S., & Asadova, B. (2024). Mycology of Fodder Plants in Different Areas of Azerbaijan the Results of Studies Devoted to the Evaluation. *Бюллетень науки и практики*, 10(10), 49-54.
12. Kurbanov, E., Aslanova, S., & Ibragimov, S. (2023). Types of Hole-Meadow and Wetlands Vegetation in Oil-contaminated Soils Siyazan District (Azerbaijan). *Bulletin of Science and Practice*, 9(3), 74-79.
13. Gurbanov, E., & Aslanova, S. (2023). Phytocenoses found in grassy mountain-meadow soils in the subalpine zone of Talish. In *Proceeding Book of 3rd International Conference on Scientific and Academic Research ICSAR (Vol. 1, No. 2, pp. 81-84)*.
14. Yusifova, A., Asadova, B., & Aslanova, S. (2025). Evaluation of Phytopathogenic Fungi According to the Degree of Danger. *Advanced Studies in Biology*, 17(1), 27-36.
15. Yusifova, A., Asadova, B., & Aslanova, S.

- (2024). GENERAL CHARACTERISTICS OF AZERBAIJAN FORAGE PLANTS AND THEIR MYCOBIOTA AND MYCOLOGICAL SAFETY PRINCIPLES APPLIED DURING USE. *Бюллетень науки и практики*, 10(8), 66-74.
16. Basti, A., & Aslanova, F. (2024). THE RELATIVE DORMANCY OF NEWLY INTRODUCED PEACH CULTIVARS CHARACTERISTIC. *Annali d'Italia* №, 60(10).
17. Асланова, Ф. (2024). АГРОБИОЛОГИЧЕСКАЯ ХАРАКТЕРИСТИКА РАЗЛИЧНЫХ СОРТОВ КУКУРУЗЫ, ВЫРАЩИВАЕМЫХ В БОГАРНЫХ УСЛОВИЯХ ЗАКАТАЛЫ, И РОЛЬ В СЕЛЕКЦИИ. *Бюллетень науки и практики*, 10(9), 102-107.
18. Gurbanov, E., Aslanova, S., & Ibrahimov, S. (2023). The Alhagieto-Salsoletum-Artemisiosum formation group at the SiyazanNefi NQCI mine. *AS-Proceedings*, 1(3), 17.
19. Gurbanov, E. M., Sh, A. S., & Asadova, B. Q. (2023). PHYTOECOLOGICAL RESEARCH ON OIL-CONTAMINATED SOILS OF "SHIRVANNEFT" OIL AND GAS DEVELOPMENT AREA AND ITS RE-CULTIVATION (AZERBAIJAN). *Труды Мордовского государственного природного заповедника им. П.Г. Смидовича*, (33), 172-183.
20. Qurbanov, E., Aslanova, S., & Ibrahimov, Ş. (2024). ŞIRVAN RAYONUNUN NEFTLƏ ÇİTKLƏNMİŞ TORPAQLARINDA RAST GƏLİNƏN YARIMSƏHRA BİTKİLİYİNİN FİTOEKOLOJİ XARAKTERİSTİKASI. *Nature & Science/Təbiət və Elm*, 6(1).
21. Эльшад, К., & Санубар, А. (2024). ЭКОЛОГИЧЕСКАЯ КЛАССИФИКАЦИЯ ПОЧВЕННО-РАСТИТЕЛЬНЫХ ТЕРРИТОРИЙ, ЗАГРЯЗНЕННЫХ МИНЕРАЛИЗОВАННЫМИ ВОДАМИ НА АПШЕРОНСКОМ ПОЛУОСТРОВЕ. *German International Journal of Modern Science/Deutsche Internationale Zeitschrift für Zeitgenössische Wissenschaft*, (75).
22. Эльшад, К., & Асланова, С. (2024). ИСТОРИЯ И ЗНАЧЕНИЕ ИЗУЧЕНИЯ ФИТОМЕЛИОРАЦИИ НЕФТЕЗАГРЯЗНЕННЫХ ЗЕМЕЛЬ В АЗЕРБАЙДЖАНЕ. *German International Journal of Modern Science/Deutsche Internationale Zeitschrift für Zeitgenössische Wissenschaft*, (80).
23. Kurbanov, E., Aslanova, S., & Ibrahimov, S. (2023). Types of Hole-Meadow and Wetlands Vegetation in Oil-contaminated Soils Siyazan District (Azerbaijan). *Bulletin of Science and Practice*, 9(3), 74-79.
24. Elshad, K., Aslanova, S., Aslanova, F., & Zviad, I. (2024). BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES. *Annali d'Italia* №, 58(3).
25. Гурбанов, Э. М., & Асланова, С. Ш. (2013). Новые местонахождения некоторых видов растений в горной части Ленкорани. *Географическая среда и живые системы*, (2), 21-24.
26. Gurbanov, E., & Aslanova, S. (2025). Study of the Area, Environmental Conditions of the "Binagadineft" NGCI Mines in the Absheron Peninsula of the Republic of Azerbaijan, and Study of Vegetation-Soil Cover Contaminated by Oil and Oil Products. *Advanced Studies in Biology*, 17(1), 11-17.